

Mapping Research Topics on Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

Dhiya Ulhaq Arkaan, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Mobile Banking in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 2004 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Mobile Banking". Based on the search results, there were 338 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Mobile Banking is divided into 6 clusters and 151 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 4 main themes related to Mobile Banking in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Mobile Banking, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

Current technological developments require all institutions to compete with each other in the technology they have. The financial industry, especially the banking sector, is very aggressive in following technological development trends. Advances in technology can help smooth transactions, such as collecting and distributing funds by adopting information technology systems. One of them is Mobile Banking.

The facilities and services offered by Mobile Banking can answer the needs of customers who want fast, safe, comfortable, cheap and available services at any time, and can be accessed from anywhere via cell phone. Especially during the pandemic conditions in the last 2 years, which limited public activities and required all workers to work from home (WFH). This makes the role of technology as a transaction medium very important. In sharia and conventional financial institutions, Mobile Banking is an important and increasingly growing service medium. Sharia and conventional banks see this opportunity in the use of technology to provide services, security and convenience in transactions with Mobile Banking.

Most international publications in the field of instrumentation are published in the Spine journal. Research regarding Mobile Banking in Islamic financial institutions increases every year. Based on searches on the Garuda page (Digital Reference Garba), there are 58 scientific studies regarding sharia Mobile Banking from 2017 to 2022. This large number of studies refers to increasingly rapid technological developments that can be implemented more deeply in sharia financial institutions.

The aim of this research is to determine the mapping of the development of Mobile Banking in Islamic financial institutions over a research period of 18 years, from 2004 to 2022, using the VOSviewer bibliometric method and literature review.

Literature Review

Mobile banking can be defined as a bank service facility that uses telecommunications devices, which allows customers to stay connected to the bank to manage accounts and access information. The existence of Mobile Banking in sharia financial institutions increases customer interest, because Mobile Banking

helps customers make transactions easily without having to queue for hours, so it can save time and energy and can be done from anywhere.

Mobile Banking is included in information technology which makes access to transactions more efficient, faster, and can be done anywhere at any time. With the development of technology, all activities can be carried out more easily through digital platforms, such as Mobile Banking which is used in sharia financial institutions to facilitate transactions such as financing quickly and efficiently as stipulated in MUI fatwa No. 117/DSN-MUI/II/2018.

Bibliometric studies are a collection of mathematical and statistical methods used to identify and measure the quantity and quality of books, articles, and journals. The bibliometric method was chosen because it can present a general picture of a research field that can be identified from scientific articles. VOSviewer is software for building and describing bibliometric networks. VOSviewer offers text development functionality that can be used to build and describe co-occurrence networks of important terms originating from scientific articles.

Literature review is a research technique for providing evidence and approaching problems or scientific processes that produce the output of a report that focuses on a study. The benefits of a literature review include showing how well researchers understand their research, developing research methods, showing the public the benefits of the research.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Mobile Banking originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Mobile Banking " for the entire year (20 04 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Based on a search for journal articles regarding Mobile Banking in sharia and conventional financial institutions in the period 2004-2022, there has been a fluctuating increase from year to year. The accumulated journals obtained during that period were 338 titles accredited as national journals. 2021 is the year with the highest number of journal publications regarding Mobile Banking, namely 87 articles.

Table 1. Journal article data about Mobile Banking is based on year _ _

Year of Publication n	Number of Publication s	Year of Publicatio n	Number of Publication s	Year of Publicatio n	Number of Publication s
2004	1	2013	3	2018	26
2006	1	2014	8	2019	42
2009	3	2015	14	2020	49
2011	1	2016	7	2021	87
2012	4	2017	14	2022	78
Number of Publication Articles 338					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Several institutions publish publications related to Mobile Banking in sharia and conventional financial institutions. The Brawijaya University FEB Student Scientific Journal is the largest journal publisher that publishes articles about Mobile Banking as many as 15 articles.

Table 2. Data from institutions and journals publishing Mobile Banking journal articles _ _

institution name	Number of Publications
FEB Student Scientific Journal, Brawijaya University	15
Accounting Journal, Udayana University	14
Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science Development, Brawijaya University	9
Journal of Business Administration, Udayana University	6
Journal of Business Management and Entrepreneurship (Tarumanegara University), Journal of Management and Business (Muhammadiyah University of Jember)	5

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 3, it is revealed that the researcher who wrote the most scientific journals about Mobile Banking in sharia and conventional financial institutions is Hasbi Assidiki Mauluddi from Bandung State Polytechnic, with 3 scientific publications.

Table 1. Researcher productivity regarding Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions indexed in GARUDA

Researcher	Number of Publications
Hasbi Assidiki Mauluddi	3
Ahmad Fauzi, Raju Wandira, Rahmatica, Phyto Min Tun, Deni Wardani	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

After searching the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), 338 scientific articles were obtained which were then exported into RIS (Research Information System) format and input for analysis using the VOSViewer application. The results of mapping visualization in the VOSViewer application regarding the development of Mobile Banking research in Islamic and conventional financial institutions are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around

Mobile Banking

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

the network visualization map of research developments regarding Mobile Banking in Islamic and Conventional financial institutions are divided into 6 clusters and 151 topics which is described as follows:

- Cluster 1, red consists of 39 topics, namely: acceptance, adoption, attitude, banking, banking service, behavioral intention, compatibility, condition, cost, credibility, data analysis technique, development, ease, effort expenditure, factor, habit, implication, individual intention, mobile banking facility, mobile banking user, partial, perceived ease, perceived usefulness, performance expectancy, pls, relative advantage, respondent, risk, social influence, square, structural equation modeling, subjective norm, tam, technology acceptance model, theory, unified theory, use behavior, usefulness, utaut.
- Cluster 2, green consists of 25 topics, namely: area, Asset, Indonesian sharia bank, bopo, coefficient, determination, equity, f test, implementation, income, increase, independent variable, indicator, ldr, m banking, npl, performance, profitability, return, roa, roe, significant difference, speed, t test, tbk.
- Cluster 3, dark blue consists of 25 topics, namely: addition, application, aspect, bca, case, curf, customer interest, effectiveness, feature, information, information quality, information system, interview, knowledge, legal protection, m bca, mobile banking application, perception, primary data, problem, service, system, system quality, usability, user satisfaction.
- Cluster 4, yellow consists of 23 topics, namely: Bank Mandiri, BNI, Covid, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, customer trust, dimension, e satisfaction, e service quality, education, enjoyment, loyalty, mobile banking service, pandemic, Persero, quality, relationship, satisfaction, service quality, smartphone, variable, word.
- Cluster 5, purple consists of 22 topics, namely: assurance, atm, convenience, decision, efficiency, empathy, hypothesis testing, interest, internet banking, multiple linear regression, multiple linear regression analysis, population, quantitative approach, quantitative research, reliability, responsiveness, security, significant influence, t count, t table, type, value.
- Cluster 6, light blue consists of 17 topics, namely: bank, banking industry, banking sector, business, case study, commercial bank, data analysis, financial inclusion, financial performance, http, impact, information technology, internet, millennial generation, mobile phone, order, org.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Mobile Banking Implementation Methods

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are more than 11 research objects regarding Mobile Banking implementation methods, namely: Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Aceh Syariah KC Lhokseumawe, Bank XYZ Airmadidi area, Bsgtouch Bank Sulutgo, BCA, Bank Sumsel Babel KCP

Tulung Absorban, Bank Panin Dubai Syariah, BUK and BUS in NTB, Bank Sumut KC Syariah Medan, Bank Kalbar, BNI KC Palembang, Bank Panin Syariah.

Based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 19 methods of implementing Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

First, Technology Acceptance Model/TAM. TAM can be applied to mobile banking by measuring how users accept and use mobile banking technology. Several steps that can be taken in implementing TAM in mobile banking are as follows: (1) Identify key variables in TAM: In implementing TAM in mobile banking, key variables that must be identified include perceived usefulness (perceived ease of use), attitude toward use, behavioral intention to use, and actual system use. (2) Data collection: Data can be collected through surveys asking mobile banking users to provide their assessments of key TAM variables. Surveys may also include questions about users' experiences with mobile banking applications, their reasons for using the application, and what factors influence their use. (3) Data analysis: The collected data can be analyzed using statistical analysis techniques such as multiple linear regression, path analysis, and validity and reliability tests. This analysis will help to understand how strong the relationship is between TAM variables and the use of mobile banking applications. (4) Interpretation of results: The results of the analysis can be interpreted to help banks understand the factors that influence user acceptance of mobile banking applications and determine appropriate strategies to increase usage. For example, if the analysis results show that convenience is the most important factor in user acceptance, the bank can consider improving features that make users feel comfortable in using the application. (5) Strategy implementation: Based on the results of the analysis and interpretation, banks can improve their mobile banking applications by adding features that make it easier for users to use the application. In addition, banks can also launch promotional campaigns to increase user awareness about the benefits of mobile banking applications and educate users on how to use them.

Second, database. Implementing a database in mobile banking is very important for storing, managing and accessing transaction information and user profiles. The following are several aspects of implementing databases in mobile banking: (1) User database: Mobile banking requires a user database that includes information such as names, email addresses, telephone numbers and passwords. This data must be stored securely and can only be accessed by users who have certain access rights. (2) Transaction database: Mobile banking must maintain user transaction records, including information such as date, time, and transaction amount. This information can be used to check a user's transaction history and ensure that the transaction was successful. (3) Bank account database: Mobile banking must be connected to the bank account database to process transactions and update user account information. This database must have secure access and should only be accessed by personnel with appropriate access rights. (4) Database Development: Mobile banking companies can develop their own database or choose to use available cloud database services. The database used should have a flexible schema to allow easy integration with mobile banking systems and applications. (5) Data Security: Implementing strict data security is essential to protect user and transaction data. Databases must be protected with strong encryption and access authentication to prevent unauthorized access.

Third, Unified Theory of Acceptance and Usage of Technology/UTAUT. In the context of mobile banking, UTAUT can be used to understand the factors that influence the use of mobile banking services by customers. Several factors that need to be considered in implementing UTAUT in mobile banking include: (1) Perceived Usefulness: Customers need to feel the benefits obtained from using mobile banking, such as ease and comfort in carrying out transactions. (2) Perceived ease of use:

Mobile banking must be easy for customers to use, including in terms of navigation and available functions. (3) Subjective Norm: The perception and influence of other people on customers' use of mobile banking can influence customers' decisions to use this service. (4) Prior Experience: Customers' previous experience with mobile technology can influence customers' perceptions and readiness in using mobile banking services. (5) Demographic factors: Factors such as age, education and gender can influence technology adoption, including the use of mobile banking.

Fourth, Customer Relationship Management/CRM Channel. Implementing Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Channels in mobile banking is a strategy that can help banks increase interactions with customers through mobile banking applications. The following are several steps that can be taken to implement CRM Channel in mobile banking: (1) Identify customer needs: Banks need to identify customer needs and preferences related to the use of mobile banking applications. This can be done by holding surveys or focus group discussions to collect information from customers about what features and services they need from the mobile banking application. (2) Personalization of services: After getting information from customers, banks need to personalize the services provided on the mobile banking application. This can be done by providing product and service recommendations based on customer profiles, as well as providing a more personalized user appearance and experience. (3) Integration with CRM systems: Mobile banking applications need to be integrated with the bank's CRM system to ensure customer information can be obtained easily by bank staff. This can also help banks provide better services to customers. (4) Proactive communication: Banks need to send proactive communications to customers via mobile banking applications. This communication can take the form of reminders about bill payment due dates or offers of products and services that suit the customer's profile. (5) Data analysis: Banks need to carry out data analysis to measure the success of CRM Channel implementation in mobile banking applications. This can be done by monitoring application usage, customer satisfaction levels, and business growth.

Fifth, E-Servqual. E-Servqual is a model for evaluating the quality of electronic services, especially online services and application-based services. To implement E-Servqual in mobile banking, there are several steps that can be taken: (1) Identify service quality factors: The first step is to identify the factors that are most important in determining the quality of mobile banking services. These factors may include system speed and reliability, ease of use, information availability, transaction security, and customer support. (2) Measuring customer expectations and perceptions: After the service quality factors have been identified, the next step is to measure customer expectations and perceptions of each factor. This can be done using a questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose. (3) Analysis of differences between expectations and perceptions: Next, the results of measuring expectations and perceptions can be tested by comparing the differences between these two values. If customer perceptions are lower than their expectations, then there is a gap in service quality that needs to be addressed. (4) Identify corrective actions: After identifying service quality gaps, the next step is to identify corrective actions that can be taken to reduce these gaps. For example, technology improvements, improved customer service, or increased transaction security. (5) Implementation of corrective actions: The final step is to implement the identified corrective actions to improve the quality of mobile banking services. This implementation may involve developing new systems, employee training, or marketing campaigns to increase customer awareness.

Fifth, Delone and McLean Model. The Delone and Mclean Model is an information system performance evaluation model which consists of six dimensions, namely system quality, information quality, user satisfaction, user intention to reuse, system use, and business impact. This model can be applied to mobile

banking to evaluate the performance of the service. The following is an explanation of the application of the Delone and Mclean Model to mobile banking: (1) System Quality: This dimension measures the extent to which the quality of the technology used to provide mobile banking services. System quality can be measured by speed, reliability, ease of use, and the features provided. (2) Information Quality: This dimension measures the extent to which the information provided by mobile banking is accurate, relevant and useful for users. Information quality can be measured from clarity, speed of access, availability of information, and level of accuracy of information. (3) User Satisfaction: This dimension measures the extent to which users are satisfied with the mobile banking services provided. User satisfaction can be measured from the user interface, ease of use, service reliability, and the level of support provided. (4) User Intention to Reuse: This dimension measures the extent to which users intend to reuse mobile banking services. User intent can be measured from user satisfaction, service reliability, ease of use, and benefits obtained. (5) System Usage: This dimension measures the extent to which users use mobile banking services. System use can be measured by frequency of use, time spent, and level of successful use. (6) Business Impact: This dimension measures the extent to which mobile banking services have an impact on the bank's business. The business impact can be measured by increasing the number of customers, increasing financial transactions, and increasing income earned.

Seventh, SWOT analysis. SWOT is an analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) which is used to evaluate the position of an organization or product in the market. Applying SWOT to mobile banking can help to identify internal and external factors that can influence the success of mobile banking services. The following is how to apply SWOT to mobile banking, namely: Identify mobile banking strengths, for example: (1) Ease of use; (2) High accessibility because it can be used anytime and anywhere; (3) Security and privacy of customer data; and (4) Ability to process transactions in real-time. Identify mobile banking weaknesses, for example: (1) Dependence on an internet connection which is sometimes unstable; (2) Data security problems that may occur if there are security gaps in the application; (3) Lack of adequate customer support to assist customers when technical problems occur; (4) Limitations in the number of transactions that can be carried out by users. Identify mobile banking opportunities, for example: (1) Changes in people's lifestyles which are increasingly mobile and completely digital; (2) Increasing number of smartphone users and internet access throughout the world; (3) Opportunities to offer new products and services, such as online investments and digital insurance; (4) Opportunities to collaborate with business partners to expand the range of products and services. Identify mobile banking threats, for example: (1) Increasing competition from other digital banking applications; (2) Cyber security threats are increasingly complex and difficult to overcome; (3) Strict and changing regulations and legal requirements; (4) Rapidly developing technology that may make mobile banking applications obsolete.

Eighth, Theory of Planned Behavior/TPB. TPB can be used to analyze and predict user behavior in using mobile banking applications. TPB consists of three factors, namely attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control. Attitude is related to an individual's evaluation of the use of mobile banking, whether they consider it useful or not, or whether the user finds it easy or difficult to use. To increase positive attitudes towards mobile banking, banking application developers need to pay attention to the appearance and functionality of the application, and make it easier for users to use. Subjective norms are related to individual perceptions about how other people (family, friends, or society) will assess the use of mobile banking. To increase subjective norms, banking application developers need to introduce mobile banking applications to the public at large, and promote the benefits and safety of using these applications. Third, perceived behavioral control is

related to individuals' perceptions of their ability to use mobile banking applications. To increase perceived behavioral control, banking application developers need to ensure the application is easy to use and makes it easy for users to access information and carry out transactions.

Ninth, Wireless Application Protocol/WAP technology. WAP is a protocol used to access information and services via wireless devices such as mobile phones. In mobile banking, WAP technology can be applied to enable users to carry out banking transactions using their mobile devices. The application of WAP technology to mobile banking usually involves the use of mobile banking applications that have been integrated with the WAP protocol. When a user performs a banking transaction, the application will send a request via the WAP protocol to the banking server, which will then process the request and send a response back to the user's mobile device. Some examples of banking transactions that can be carried out via WAP technology in mobile banking include: (1) Check balance and transaction history, namely users can check account balances and recent transaction history via mobile banking applications connected to the WAP protocol; (2) Transfer money between bank accounts, i.e. users can transfer money between registered bank accounts via a mobile banking application connected to the WAP protocol; (3) Bill payment, namely users can pay bills via a mobile banking application connected to the WAP protocol. For example, electricity bills, telephone bills, internet bills, and so on.

Tenth, Java 2 Micro Edition/J2ME. J2ME is a mobile application development platform that was quite popular in the past. Implementing J2ME in mobile banking can enable users to carry out banking transactions via their cellphones. The following are several steps in implementing J2ME in mobile banking: (1) Identify business needs and user requirements which involves determining what features are needed by users, such as fund transfers, bill payments, and so on; (2) Design the application architecture. The application architecture must be able to handle a variety of different types of mobile devices and be able to interact with the bank's backend; (3) Create a user interface, namely the user interface must be easy to use and allow users to carry out banking transactions easily. It should also consider security factors, such as authentication and data encryption; (4) Integration with the bank's backend system, namely the mobile banking application must be connected to the bank's existing backend system and be able to carry out banking transactions safely and efficiently; (5) Test the application, namely the application must be tested carefully to ensure that all features function correctly and the application runs smoothly; and (6) Application launch, namely after the application has finished testing, the application can be launched to users.

Eleventh, Neural Networks. The application of Neural Networks in mobile banking can help improve the security and efficiency of banking services provided in mobile banking applications. Some examples of the application of Neural Networks in mobile banking include: (1) Fraud Detection: Neural Networks can be used to detect suspicious activity in mobile banking applications, such as unusual user activity or suspicious transaction patterns. This can help reduce the risk of fraud and cheating in banking transactions. (2) Credit Risk Analysis: Neural Networks can be used to generate credit risk scores and help decide whether a loan will be approved or not. These models can process data such as credit history, income, and other personal data to estimate credit risk and determine appropriate interest rates. (3) Smart Chatbots: Neural Networks can be used to build smart chatbots that can process customer requests and provide precise and fast answers. This can improve customer service efficiency and help increase customer satisfaction. (4) Sentiment Analysis: Neural Networks can be used to analyze the sentiments of customers displayed on social media platforms. This can help banks understand customer preferences and behavior to improve customer experience. (5) Customer Behavior Prediction: Neural Networks can be used to predict customer behavior based on

historical data and customer profiles. This can help banks provide more personalized service and increase customer loyalty.

Twelfth, Structural Equation Model/SEM. Structural Equation Model (SEM) is a statistical method that can be used to test the relationship between different variables in a complex model. Applying SEM to mobile banking can help understand the factors that influence the use of mobile banking applications, as well as obtain information that is useful in optimizing the use of these applications. The following are several steps that can be taken in applying SEM to mobile banking: (1) Identify the variables that will be included in the SEM model, for example variables that influence the use of mobile banking such as usability, trust, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and so forth; (2) Create an SEM model using available SEM software such as AMOS, EQS, or Mplus, where the SEM model must consist of several simultaneous equations and parameters that must be estimated; (3) Collect data from respondents who have used the mobile banking application, this data will be used to test the SEM model; (4) Analyze the collected data using the selected SEM software, where in SEM analysis, parameter significance testing must be carried out to ensure that the model created truly represents the data; (5) After the analysis is carried out, interpret the results by paying attention to the significance value, coefficient of determination (R-square), as well as other statistical values such as goodness-of-fit index (GFI), comparative fit index (CFI), and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA).

Thirteenth, User Experience Questionnaire/UEQ. Implementing UEQ in mobile banking can be done using the following steps: (1) Determine the UEQ scale that will be used. UEQ consists of six dimensions, namely: Beauty, Efficiency, Novelty, Perspicuity, Dependability, and Stimulation. Each dimension has four value scales (valued 1 to 4), namely: strongly disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree. (2) Create a UEQ questionnaire that is appropriate to the mobile banking application you want to evaluate. The UEQ questionnaire can be created by referring to previously determined UEQ dimensions. (3) Ask participants to fill out the UEQ questionnaire. Participants can be selected randomly from existing mobile banking application users. (4) Provide instructions for participants to download and install the mobile banking application on their devices, and then use it to perform certain tasks, such as transferring money, paying bills, or checking balances. (5) After participants have finished using the application, ask them to fill out the UEQ questionnaire. Be sure to provide clear instructions and remind participants that their responses are critical to helping improve the quality of the mobile banking application being evaluated. (6) Analyze data from the UEQ questionnaire that has been filled in by participants. In analyzing this data, the average UEQ value of each dimension can be calculated and the total UEQ value can be calculated. The results of this data analysis will provide a general picture of the quality of the user experience on the mobile banking application being evaluated. (7) Evaluate and develop a mobile banking application based on the results of the UEQ data analysis that has been obtained. This is done to improve the user experience and quality of the mobile banking application.

Fourteenth, Usability Testing. Implementing Usability Testing in mobile banking is a process for evaluating user experience in using mobile banking applications. The aim of Usability Testing is to ensure that the mobile banking application is easy to use, efficient, and provides added value for users. The following are several stages that can be followed to implement Usability Testing in mobile banking: (1) Determine the objectives and testing criteria, including what functions will be tested, what features will be tested, and the target audience that will be tested; (2) Create a test plan that includes the steps to be taken during testing, such as functionality tests, interface suitability, and ease of use; (3) Recruit participants who are potential users of mobile banking applications to test the application and provide

feedback. Ensure that the number of participants is sufficient to obtain accurate results; (4) Carry out testing by proposing a series of tasks that must be completed by participants. Pay attention to and note any issues discovered and consider participant feedback in application development; (5) Analyze test results to identify problems and errors found during testing, as well as to evaluate whether the application meets the test criteria; (6) Fix problems and errors found during testing and test again to ensure the application is fixed and meets the testing criteria.

Fifteenth, System Usability Scale/SUS. SUS is a useful measurement tool for evaluating the usability and ease of use of a system, including mobile banking applications. The following are several steps that can be taken to implement SUS in mobile banking: (1) Determine the measurement objectives and what you want to measure with SUS. Goals can range from evaluating the general use of an application to improving specific features or functions; (2) Identify the people who will be used as respondents in the SUS assessment. Select mobile banking application users representing various user groups, including new users and experienced users; (3) Give respondents instructions on how they should complete the SUS questionnaire. Be sure to provide information about the purpose of the measurement, that their responses are anonymous, and how to complete the questionnaire; (4) Give the SUS questionnaire to respondents and ensure that they have understood the instructions. The SUS questionnaire consists of 10 questions related to the usability and ease of use of the system. The questions in this questionnaire are designed to measure user perceptions of system performance; (5) After the respondent has filled out the SUS questionnaire, evaluate the results to determine the level of usability and ease of use of the mobile banking application. The results obtained can provide information about areas that need to be improved in mobile banking application development; (6) If there are areas that need improvement, then implement improvements to the mobile banking application. After implementation is carried out, carry out another evaluation using the SUS questionnaire to measure changes in the usability and ease of use of the mobile banking application.

Sixteenth, Support Vector Machine. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a machine learning technique that can be used to build classification and regression models. SVM has been used in areas such as facial recognition, credit card fraud detection, and sentiment analysis. In the context of mobile banking, SVM can be applied to build classification models to recognize suspicious or fraudulent transaction patterns. SVM can retrieve historical transaction data from users, such as amount, time, transaction type, and location, and then build a model to recognize suspicious patterns. SVM can classify transactions into two categories: normal transactions and suspicious transactions. If a transaction is classified as suspicious, the system can take appropriate action, such as requesting additional confirmation from the user or blocking the transaction. SVM can also be applied in mobile banking to build a prediction model to determine whether a user will carry out a certain transaction or not. In this case, SVM can take into account factors such as previous transaction history, time of day, transaction type, and location to make predictions. However, before SVM can be applied to mobile banking, several things need to be done such as: (1) Prepare the required data correctly, such as historical transaction data, and select the most relevant features to be used in the SVM model; (2) Choosing the right type of kernel to use in SVM, such as a linear kernel or a non-linear kernel; (3) Training the SVM model with sufficient data to ensure the model has good accuracy; and (4) Conduct regular evaluations to ensure the model is still effective and accurate in recognizing suspicious patterns or predicting transactions.

Seventeenth, Lexicon Based Features. Lexicon Based Features is a text analysis method that involves natural language processing to identify sentiment or emotion from a text. This method can be applied to mobile banking to analyze sentiment or emotions from customer feedback on mobile banking services. The

following are several steps that can be taken to implement Lexicon Based Features in mobile banking: (1) First of all, it is necessary to collect data containing customer feedback on mobile banking services. This data can be collected through customer surveys, mobile banking app reviews, or through social media. (2) The next step is to create a dictionary containing a list of words with positive and negative sentiments. This dictionary can be created by selecting a list of words from an existing dictionary, or by creating a new dictionary using a text classification algorithm. (3) Once the data and dictionary are prepared, the text received from the customer can be processed using a text classification algorithm. This algorithm will identify words that have positive or negative sentiment and assign a sentiment score to each text. (4) Sentiment analysis: Once the text is processed, the results can be analyzed to determine the sentiment of customer feedback. Sentiment analysis can be done by counting the number of positive and negative feedback, or by calculating the average sentiment score of all feedback. (5) The results of sentiment analysis can be used to make improvements to mobile banking services. For example, if the analysis results show that most customers complain about difficulty using a particular feature, developers can improve the feature to improve the user experience.

Eighteenth, UX Curve. UX Curve is a model used to describe the user experience from the beginning to the end of interaction with a product or service. Applying this model to mobile banking can help to improve the quality of user experience on mobile banking applications. The following are the stages of implementing UX Curve in mobile banking: (1) Awareness, the first stage is to make potential users aware of the existence of the mobile banking application and the benefits that can be obtained by using it. Some ways that can be done include: Advertising mobile banking applications on online platforms such as websites, social media, or other advertising platforms; Include information regarding mobile banking applications on other banking services, such as ATM machines or internet banking; Provide special incentives or promos for new users who register and use the mobile banking application. (2) Acquisition, after attracting the attention of potential users, the next stage is to make users interested in downloading and trying the mobile banking application. Several ways that can be done include: Providing a clear display and information regarding the benefits and convenience that can be obtained by using the mobile banking application; Ensure that the process of registering and downloading the mobile banking application is easy and simple; Use positive reviews from other users as a reference. (3) Activation, after the user downloads the mobile banking application, the next step is to make the user actively use the application. Some ways that can be done include: Providing features that are easy for users to understand and use; Providing guides or tutorials in mobile banking applications that are easy for users to understand; Provide incentives or rewards to users who use the mobile banking application within a certain time. (4) Retention, this stage is related to how to produce a good user experience and make users continue to use the mobile banking application. Several ways that can be done include: Providing features that are relevant and easy to use; Providing convenience in terms of application use and navigation; Prioritize security in every transaction and protect user personal data. (5) Referrals/recommendations, the final stage of the UX Curve is generating positive recommendations from users to other people. Some ways that can be done include: Providing a referral or promotional program for users who recommend the mobile banking application to other people; Increase user trust by showing that the mobile banking application has good security and privacy; Improving service quality and responsiveness in responding to requests and input from users.

Nineteenth, Near Field Communication Technology with Android-Based Operating System. Near Field Communication (NFC) Technology is a technology that allows devices to communicate wirelessly with other NFC-enabled devices at very

short distances. In the context of mobile banking, implementing NFC can enable users to make transactions by simply touching their cellphone to an NFC-enabled payment device, such as a credit card machine or ATM. To implement NFC in mobile banking with the Android operating system, there are several steps that need to be taken: (1) Ensure that the cellphone used has an NFC chip and an Android operating system that supports NFC technology; (2) Users need to activate the NFC feature on their phones. This can be done through the settings menu on the Android device; (3) Make sure the mobile banking application used supports NFC to carry out transactions in this way; (4) When making a transaction, users can touch their phone to an NFC-enabled payment device. The mobile banking application will process the transaction and send the information needed to complete the payment; (5) After the transaction has been processed, the user will receive payment confirmation via the mobile banking application.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Influence of Mobile Banking

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are more than 11 research objects regarding the influence caused by the existence of Mobile Banking services, namely: BRI Syariah KC Pekanbaru, BCA KC Karawang, customers in Chennai, India, BNI KC Mamuju, BSI KC Monginsidi Jakarta, Bank DKI, Bank Sinarmas KC Teluk Betung Lampung, Bank Mandiri KC Bengkalis, BSM KCP Muara Bungo, BSI KC Palembang Simpang Patal, BSM KC Jemur Handayani Surabaya.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 30 influences caused by the presence of Mobile Banking services, namely: (1) Speed of information; (2) Service standards; (3) E-Loyalty; (4) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; (5) Return On Assets/ROA; (6) Return On Equity/ROE; (7) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR; (8) Payback Period/PP; (9) Return On Investment/ROI; (10) Net Present Value/NPV; (11) Internal Rate of Return/IRR; (12) Profitability Index/PI; (13) Operational Expenses to Operational Income/BOPO; (14) Transaction volume; (15) Non Performing Loans/NPL; (16) Net profit; (17) Banking financial inclusion; (18) Rural communities; (19) Digitalization of Sharia Finance; (20) Inclusive Finance; (21) MSMEs in the Surabaya region; (22) Customer satisfaction; (23) Asset growth; (24) Third Party Funds/DPK; (25) Net Profit Margin/NPM; (26) E-Commerce; (27) Fee Based Income; (28) Prevention of criminal acts of corruption; (29) Earnings Per Share/EPS; (30) Customer behavior.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinants of Interest in Using Mobile Banking

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are more than 75 research objects regarding the discussion of determinants of customer interest in using Mobile Banking, namely: BCA in Jabodetabek, BCA KC Malang, BCA Jambi, BCA Banda Aceh, BNI KC Yogyakarta, BNI KC Makassar, BNI KC UGM, BNI KC Depok, BNI KC Sukabumi, BNI KC Sukoharjo, BNI KC Unitomo Surabaya, BNI KC Harmoni, BNI KC Palu, BNI Syariah KC Depok, BNI Syariah KCP Taba Jemekeh Lubuklinggau, CIMB Niaga, Bank Sulselbar KC Binjai, Bank Mandiri KC Sam Ratulangi, Bank Mandiri KC Surabaya, Bank Mandiri KC Makassar, BSM KCP Belawan, BSM KCP Tangerang BSD, BSM KCP Ulee Kareng Banda Aceh, BSM KCP Semarang, BSM KCP Lhokseumawe, BSM KC Palopo City, Bank Kalsel Banjarmasin Main Branch, Banks in Myanmar, BRI KC Makassar, BRI KC Kebumen, BRI KC Bengkulu, BRI KC Ciputat, BRI KC Renon, BRI KC Manna, BRI KC Rembang, BRI KC Malang Kawi, BRI KC Buntok, BRI KC Depok, BRI KCP Universitas Brawijaya, BRI KC Cirebon, BRI KC Semarang Pandanaran, BRI Syariah KC Jombang, Bank Artha Graha, BTN KC Makassar, Bank Jabar Banten, Bank Danamon, Bank Mega, Bank Mega Syariah KC Palu, BSI KC Lhokseumawe, BSI KC

Bengkulu, BSI KC Perbaungan, BSI KC Tangerang, Bank NTB Syariah KC Sumbawa, Bank NTB Syariah KC Alas, Bank NTB Syariah KCP Bolo, Bank NTT KC Ende, Bank DKI KC Surabaya, Bank Sinarmas KC Malang, bank customers in Ambon Regency, customers banks in Malang City, bank customers in Jambi Province, bank customers in East Kalimantan Province, bank customers in DKI Jakarta Province, Indonesian migrant workers, Bank Muamalat Indonesia KCP Kudus, BNI Syariah KC Banda Aceh, Iran, South Africa, BPD Bali Denpasar Branch, BPD Koto Baru Dharmasraya, Bank Nagari, students in DKI Jakarta, Bank Jatim Pare, Bank Muamalat KC Medan, BTPN KC Manado.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 76 determinants of customer interest in using Mobile Banking, namely: (1) Access; (2) Costs; (3) Culture; (4) Brand image; (5) Design; (6) Demographics; (7) Government support; (8) Efficiency; (9) Effectiveness; (10) Performance expectations; (11) Business expectations; (12) Self-efficacy; (13) Facilities; (14) Features; (15) Framing; (16) Lifestyle; (17) Gender; (18) Television Advertisements; (19) Informative; (20) Innovative; (21) Security; (22) Happiness; (23) Need; (24) Reliability; (25) Usefulness; (26) Convenience; (27) Enjoyment; (28) Satisfaction; (29) Practicality; (30) Convenience; (31) Excellence; (32) Conformity; (33) Relative advantage; (34) Trust; (35) Commitment; (36) Communication; (37) Credibility; (38) Service quality; (39) Financial literacy; (40) Digital literacy; (41) Loyalty; (42) Electronic Services/E-Servqual; (43) Macro and Micro Social Environment; (44) Benefits; (45) Hedonic motivation; (46) Customer intentions; (47) Sustainable intentions; (48) Added value; (49) Covid-19 Pandemic; (50) Knowledge; (51) Income; (52) Education; (53) Perception of convenience; (54) Perception of use; (55) Perception of Fraud; (56) Control of opportunistic behavior; (57) Personalization; (58) Employment; (59) Experience; (60) Privacy; (61) Promotion; (62) Performance; (63) Consumer psychographics; (64) Recommendations; (65) Reputation; (66) Risk; (67) Attitude; (68) System; (69) Sociality; (70) Social media; (71) Spirituality; (72) Technology; (73) Age; (74) Career women in Indonesia and Bangladesh; (75) Website; and (76) Word of Mouth

Mapping Literature Review regarding Mobile Banking Services

Based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are more than 4 research objects regarding Mobile Banking services, namely: Bank Sinar Harapan Bali Operational Head Office, students of the Innayatullah Banyuasin Islamic Boarding School, BPD Aceh.

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 9 problems surrounding Mobile Banking services, namely: (1) Determining the basic price of services; (2) Responsibility for transaction failure; (3) Education and training on the use of Mobile Banking; (4) Customer protection regarding the use of Mobile Banking; (5) Protection of confidentiality of customer personal data; (6) Risk management; (7) Criminal acts related to Mobile Banking account access; (8) Factors inhibiting interest in using Mobile Banking: Limited information, costs, traditions, registration complexity; and (9) SPP payments.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- Number of research publications around Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 2004 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 338 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the FEB Student Scientific Journal, Brawijaya University, which is the journal

publisher that publishes the most articles about Mobile. Banking as many as 15 articles.

- The most productive researcher in publishing research results is Hasbi Assidiki Mauluddi from Bandung State Polytechnic, with 3 scientific publications.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 6 clusters and 151 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 39 topics, cluster 2 consists of 25 topics, cluster 3 consists of 25 topics, cluster 4 consists of 23 topics, cluster 5 consists of 22 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 17 topics.
- Based on the literature review, there are 4 main research themes, namely: (1) Methods for implementing Mobile Banking; (2) Influence of Mobile Banking; (3) Determinants of interest in using Mobile Banking; and (4) Mobile Banking Services.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

References

- Abidin, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Third-Party Fund (DPK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117572>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117521>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Kompilasi Hukum Ekonomi Syariah (KHES): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078577>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds (Reksa Dana): Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117306>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reksa Dana Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078579>
- Al-Ghozy, H. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Musaqah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117769>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing (Perataan Laba) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078569>

- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117537>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Garansi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077304>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Guarantees on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117749>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117698>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077344>
- Anggreni, L. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Ijarah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117783>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Operasional pada Industri Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ekonomi Islam*, 14(2), 158–174. <https://doi.org/10.22236/jei.v14i2.11121>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Reputasi pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada

- Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Research Mapping on Credit Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117751>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117611>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117607>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117603>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Current Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117601>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117564>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Per Share in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117548>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Economic Value Added (EVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117545>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financial Value Added (FVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117539>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financing Risk in Islamic and*

Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117292>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jualah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117779>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Mapping Research on the Ratio of Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117623>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Operating Margin (NOM) on Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117324>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Profit Margin (NPM) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117320>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Non Performing Financing (NPF) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117318>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAFTA (Journal of Accounting, Finance, Taxation & Auditing)*, 4(2), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jafta.v4i2.7650>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio On

- Investment (ROI) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Total Asset Turnover (TATO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 20(2), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.36406/jam.v20i2.975>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117288>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117316>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Return On Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117286>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharf on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117759>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117619>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Total Asset Turnover (TATO) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142629>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117154>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan*

- Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117529>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jaminan/Agunan pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078573>
- Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117329>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Elkhori, N. E. M., Safira, W. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Denda pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078519>
- Emiliani, E., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117785>
- Faiz, M. W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Safe Deposit Box pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078581>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117747>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077317>
- Farida, M., Andrini, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogasi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078583>
- Farida, M., Andrini, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117160>
- Fauzan, I. F. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117745>

- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *Pengaruh Pengetahuan, Kepercayaan, Produk, Pelayanan, dan Religiusitas terhadap Minat Menabung*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117278>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). The Effect of Knowledge, Trust, Products, Services and Religiosity on Interest in Saving. *The 9th International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business (ICONIES 2023)*, 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037033>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117743>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077588>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Pembangunan Daerah (BPD) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077610>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117690>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Return On Equity (ROE) in Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117294>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Equity (ROE) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117712>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078459>
- Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117328>
- Laksana, E. Y., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117554>
- Laksana, Y. E., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dewan*

- Pengawas Syariah (DPS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078565>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117662>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117678>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078436>
- Nursaputri, D. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Muzara'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117767>
- Panatagama, A. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117755>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117740>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077628>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Murabaha on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117771>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117670>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Rahn (Pawn) on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117763>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117757>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Maybank Sharia and*

Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117627>

- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Maybank Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117629>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmah, R. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Application of Financial Accounting Standard Statements (PSAK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117314>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping around the Determinant Variables of Return on Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117298>
- Saputra, H. M. G. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117332>
- Saputri, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117533>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Salam on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117761>
- Suwandini, F. K. T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometric.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117684>
- Syarifah, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Qard on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117765>

- Ummah, F. K., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional Majelis Ulama Indonesia (DSN-MUI) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078567>
- Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117704>
- Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10075718>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Istisna' on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117781>